

Stellar evolution

Highlight of evolution of main sequence, subgiants and red giant stars

MarieJo Goupil

LESIA, Observatoire de Paris

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- I. Introduction
- II. General framework
- III. Evolution of a $1M_{\odot}$ star
- IV. Evolution of a $1.3M_{\odot}$ star
- V. Some open issues

Basic references and further reading

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I. Introduction

Some definitions

- **Stellar evolution** := evolution with time of the structure of a star
- **Stellar structure** := $\rho(r)$, $\rho(r)$, $\nabla(r)$, $X(t)$, $Y(t)$, localization of radiative and convective regions

Observed distribution of stars in a color-magnitude diagram

- Color -magnitude diagram for the Gaia DR3 (4,276,690 stars)
- The colour scale represents the square root of the density of stars.
- Most stars are clustered in specific regions in the HR diagram. This reflects the effects of stellar evolution.
- One clearly notices the densier regions MS (H burning) and red clump (He burning).

Stars observed by Gaia. (Credit: Gaia collaboration, Babusiaux+2022)

Variety of masses and ages! dispersion due to various chemical composition, rotation, activity, binarity

Standard model evolution

- Standard stellar models : ignore rotation, magnetic fields , binarity
- Star formation and end of life : out of scope
- Evolution depends on the initial
 - mass M , of the star
 - chemical composition (hydrogen X_0 , helium Y_0 and traces of heavier elements Z_0)*
 - physical laws
 - free parameters $\alpha_{MLT}, \alpha_{ov}$ when the physics is poorly described (3D processes cast into 1D evolution)

* *relative mass abundance*

- This lecture focuses on the evolution of **low mass** stars with masses
 $\sim 0.8M_{\odot} < M < 1.5M_{\odot}$

(Reason: those stars show solar-like oscillations at some phases of their evolution)

- This lecture assumes an initial **solar** chemical composition only
($X_0 \sim 0.7$, $Y_0 \sim 0.25$, $Z_0 \sim 0.012$)

Evolution starts at the pre-main sequence (PMS) phase when the star reaches quasi hydrostatic equilibrium

$$\frac{dp}{dr} = -\rho g \quad ; \quad g = \frac{gm(r)}{r^2}$$

but thermally unstable

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dl}{dm} &= \epsilon - T \frac{dS}{dt} \\ &= 0 \quad \neq 0 \end{aligned}$$

Why do stars evolve ?

- Stars evolve because they radiate their energy away at their surface :
black body radiation : $L \propto R^2 T_{eff}^4$
- This loss of energy must be compensated by an internal source of energy to maintain its equilibrium
- When the supply of energy is not sufficient, the pressure cannot compete with the gravity and the star readjusts its structure (evolves) in order to find a new equilibrium state
- The life of a star is an alternance of equilibrium phases and unstable phases
- 'The life of the star is a permanent fight against its own gravity' !

What are the available sources of energy ?

- Available sources of energy for a star :
 - gravitational energy (the star contracts) and/or
 - nuclear energy (requires high temperatures, localized)

Time scales

The time scale ordering is

$$t_{dyn} \ll t_{KH}^{(*)} \ll t_{nuc}^{(*)}$$

- For the Sun, $27mn \ll 3.1 \cdot 10^7 yrs \ll 9 \cdot 10^9 yrs$
- The Sun evolves on the nuclear time scale, it will remain on the MS for $t_{nuc} \sim 9 \cdot 10^9$ yrs where it will have converted 10% of its H mass into He
- The actual Sun has burned about half of the available fuel and is ~ 4.6 Gyr old.

$(*)t_{KH} = E_{grav}/L$; $t_{nuc} = r \times \text{available nuclear energy}/L$, $r = \text{energy release efficiency of the nuclear reactions}$

Numerical computation of stellar evolution

Given the total mass M and the initial chemical composition $\{X\}_i$:

Credit: R. Ouazzani, priv. comm.

II General framework

Theoretical HR Diagram : dependency with mass and age

Evolutionary tracks for various masses from the main sequence up to the red giant branch. Evolution from left to right i.e for decreasing effective temperature. (kindly provided by A. Noels, private comm.)

Theoretical HR Diagram : specific evolutionary tracks

Credit Basti grids (open line)

Low mass stars evolve successively through **PMS**, **MS**, **subgiant** and **red giant** phases and further on up to their end of life as white dwarfs.

Qualitative behavior in the Hertzsprung-Rüssel diagram

One distinguishes three types of phase:

Credit. K Belkacem, priv.com.

Energy transport processes and temperature gradient

- **Schwarzschild criterion:** convection sets in whenever

$$\nabla_{rad} > \nabla_{ad}$$

- Radiative regions (diffusion process): $\nabla = \nabla_{rad} \propto \kappa \frac{l}{m}$
 κ opacity, coefficient of absorption of radiation

- Convective regions (macroscopic motions) for an ideal gas :

$$\nabla = \nabla_{ad} \sim \frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma} \sim 2/5 \text{ for a monoatomic gas}$$

(*) Temperature gradient $\nabla = \frac{d \ln T}{d \ln P}$

Qualitative behavior in the Hertzsprung-Rüssel diagram

1) Cool side : convective transport dominates (PMS, red giants)

- κ (ions H^-) $\propto T^9$
- $\nabla_{rad} \propto \kappa \gg \nabla_{ad}$
- One also shows $T_{eff} \propto L^{0.01}$
Hence the track remains essentially vertical because T_{eff} is nearly independent of L .

Credit. K Belkacem, priv.com.

Qualitative behavior in the Hertzsprung-Rüssel diagram

2) Phases dominated by the radiative transport (PMS arrival onto the ZAMS, subgiants)

- With $\kappa \propto \rho T^{-3.5}$ (Kramers' opacity) in that regime, one shows that $L \propto T_{eff}^\beta$ with $\beta = 0$:

L is independent of T_{eff} leading to a nearly horizontal track

Credit. K Belkacem, priv.com.

Transition from convective to radiative dominant transport

- **Virial theorem** : For an ideal gas in hydrostatic equilibrium, $E_{grav} + 2E_{kin} = 0$
- $R \downarrow$: half of energy of contraction is radiated away, half increases the internal energy : $T \uparrow$
- This causes ionization which decreases the opacity $\kappa \propto \rho T^{-3.5}$ (Kramers' opacity)
- $\kappa \downarrow, \nabla_{rad} \downarrow$
- This tends to quench convection first at the center where the temperature is the highest

$$T \uparrow, \kappa \downarrow, \nabla_{rad} \rightarrow < \nabla_{ad}$$

Qualitative behavior in the Hertzsprung-Rüssel diagram

3) Phases dominated by production of nuclear energy

- Regions dominated by the production of nuclear energy (H, He, bent area, red for the MS one).
- On the main sequence, there exists a **mass-luminosity relation**:

$$L \propto M^s, \quad s \sim 3.5 \text{ for } \sim 1M_{\odot}$$

Credit. K Belkacem, priv.com.

III. Low mass star evolution

In the following, one considers the evolution of a $1M_{\odot}$ star as typical **low mass stars**. Differences when the mass of the star is $1.3M_{\odot}$ will then be highlighted.

- Low mass stars ignite helium in the core under degenerate conditions.
- This occurs in the mass range $\sim 0.48M_{\odot}$ and $\sim 2M_{\odot}$.
- The lower limit is the critical mass needed to ignite hydrogen,
- The upper limit depends on the chemical composition of the stars. Above that mass, stars ignite core hydrogen in non degenerate conditions

II. Evolution of a $1M_{\odot}$ star

Pre-Main sequence: Definition

- During the gravitational contraction of a molecular cloud, a protostar accretes matter.
- When accretion slows down and the final mass is approached, the photosphere of the protostar becomes visible.
- The star is cool and fully convective, it arrives onto the **Hayashi line** (where $\nabla = \nabla_{ad}$) at $T_{eff} \sim 3000 - 4000\text{K}$

That is when the Pre-Main Sequence starts (PMS)

PMS: why does gravitational contraction in the PMS occur?

- The star evolves quasi-hydrostatically on a time scale $t_{KH} \sim 10^7$ yrs.
- The star is too cool to ignite nuclear hydrogen burning
- The whole star undergoes a **quasi-homologous gravitational contraction** which provides its energy source.
- The energy source is well spread out over the whole star.
- Contraction $R \downarrow$, $T_{eff} \sim \text{constant}$, $L \downarrow$

III. Evolution of a $1M_{\odot}$ star

PMS: gravitational contraction

The PMS track in a HR diagram is made of two successive steps:

1) the contracting structure remains fully convective

$R \downarrow, L \downarrow$ but central temperatures $T_c \uparrow$

PMS evolution : magenta (fully convective phase)

III. Evolution of a $1M_{\odot}$ star

PMS: gravitational contraction

The PMS track in a HR diagram is made of two successive phases:

2) the star develops a radiative core

$$T \uparrow, \kappa \downarrow, \nabla_{rad} \rightarrow < \nabla_{ad}$$

PMS evolution : magenta (radiative transport dominated phase)

After 50 Myr have passed, the star reaches the main sequence.

MS: a long stable phase

- From now on, the star settles in the **main sequence (MS)**
- In the central regions, H is converted into He: 4 protons give one He nucleus ($2p + 2p$)
- bottleneck : $p + p \rightarrow d$ (one $p \rightarrow n$)
- The released nuclear energy maintains the star in equilibrium.

$$\frac{dl}{dm} = \epsilon_{nuc} - T \frac{dS}{dt}$$
$$\neq 0 \qquad = 0$$

- The nuclear production is regulated so that it can balance the energy losses by radiation at the surface.

III. Evolution of $1M_{\odot}$ star

MS: a long stable phase

- The MS-phase corresponds to a stable phase of about 9 – 10 Gyr
- It is the longest phase in the evolution of a star
- The MS-phase starts at **ZAMS**^(*) and ends at **TAMS**^(**).

MS evolution (magenta): stable phase when the star luminosity and effective temperature vary little.

(*) Zero Age Main Sequence, criterion $L_g/L_{\text{nuc}} < 1\%$.

(**) Terminal Age Main Sequence, (criterion $X_c \sim 10^{-4}$).

Why MS is a stable phase?

The reason is that when the gas is ideal $P \propto \rho T$, there exists a **thermostatic control of the pressure** and the star is a stable nuclear reactor

III. Evolution of $1M_{\odot}$ star

Why MS is a stable phase?

For a given mass,

$$\text{Hydrostatic eq.: } P \sim \frac{GM^2}{R^4} \text{ then } \frac{dP}{P} = -4 \frac{dR}{R}$$

$$\text{Mass conservation : } \rho \propto \frac{M}{R^3} \text{ then } \frac{d\rho}{\rho} = -3 \frac{dR}{R}$$

so that

$$\frac{dP}{P} = \frac{4}{3} \frac{d\rho}{\rho}$$

Assume EOS: $P \propto \rho^{\alpha} T^{\delta}$ then

$$\frac{dP}{P} = \alpha \frac{d\rho}{\rho} + \delta \frac{dT}{T}$$

From Kippenhahn, Weigert & Weiss 1989

Why MS is a stable phase?

then

$$\frac{d\rho}{\rho} = \frac{\delta}{4/3 - \alpha} \frac{dT}{T}$$

- Energy conservation (first principle and quasistatic evolution)

$$\delta Q = TdS = c_v dT + Pd(1/\rho) = c_v dT - \frac{P}{\rho} \frac{d\rho}{\rho} = c_* dT$$

where

$$c_* = c_v - \left(\frac{P}{\rho T} \right) \frac{\delta}{4/3 - \alpha}$$

Why MS is a stable phase?

$$\delta Q = c_* dT \quad c_* = c_v - \frac{2}{3} \frac{\delta}{4/3 - \alpha} c_v$$

$$P \propto \rho^\alpha T^\beta$$

- Ideal gas : $\alpha = 1 = \delta \rightarrow c_* = -c_v < 0$

Assume some excess of ϵ : $\delta Q > 0$ then

$$\delta Q = -c_v dT > 0$$

then $T \downarrow$; $\epsilon \downarrow$ cooling and back to 'normal'

Ignition of core hydrogen in ideal gas conditions : stable phase because $P(\rho, T)$

A short detour : the Helium flash

- Electron degeneracy conditions : $\alpha = 5/3; \delta = 0$ ($P \propto \rho$ only) $\rightarrow c_* = c_v > 0$

Assume some excess of ϵ : $\delta Q > 0$ then

$$\delta Q = c_v dT > 0$$

then $T \uparrow, \epsilon \propto T^{16}, T \uparrow \dots$ no control of the pressure: thermal runaway

- Ignition of core Helium burning at the tip of the red giant branch in degenerate conditions because $P(\rho)$: thermal run away
- A huge increase of luminosity locally
- The sudden increase of T partially lifts the degeneracy
- After several flashes each closer to the center, the helium core is no longer degenerate and burns quietly after this event :the star is on the red clump

A slow evolution of the chemical composition in the MS

- The central region (core) of low mass stars being radiative, the MS stars become more and more inhomogeneous.
- $X_c \downarrow$ with time; $Y_c \uparrow$ then $\mu_c^{(*)} \uparrow$

Evolution with time of the hydrogen abundance profile in a low mass star in the main sequence

Credit: Phil Armitage <https://jila.colorado.edu/~pja/stars02/>

$$(*) \mu_c = (1/2 + (3/2)X - Y/2)^{-1}$$

Mass-luminosity- chemical composition relation

The MS luminosity depends on the mass and the chemical composition

$$L \sim \frac{1}{Z(1+X)} \frac{1}{R^{0.5}} M^{4.5} \mu^{7.5}$$

$$T_{\text{eff}} \propto \left(\frac{L}{R^2}\right)^{1/4} \sim \left(\frac{\mu^{7.5}}{R^{5/2}}\right)^{1/4} \sim \mu^{2.3} \uparrow$$

$\mu_c \uparrow \rightarrow L \uparrow$

III. Evolution of $1M_{\odot}$ star

Slowly moving in the MS in the HR diagram

- The slow evolution of the structure causes the star to change slowly its position in the HR diagram $L \uparrow, T_{eff} \uparrow$

Slow evolution in the main sequence (magenta). Yellow cross represents the present Sun.

The end of the main sequence

- With H burning dominantly via the pp chain: the core is radiative. H-Depletion starts at $X = 0$ at $r = 0$ and extends progressively upward.
- the H-burning shell sets in gradually above the growing Helium core
- Stellar evolutionary calculations show that the star begins to evolve rapidly when approximately 10% of the initial amount of hydrogen is converted.
- The star then leaves the MS.

Hydrogen (X) and Helium profile (Y) in a mid main sequence low mass star. Credit: Phil Armitage <https://jila.colorado.edu/~pja/stars02/>

Beyond the main sequence : H shell burning

Formation of an isothermal contracting core

The central regions contract and heat up

- When hydrogen is exhausted in the central regions, nuclear reactions stop there.
- With the disappearance of the energy supply to balance energy surface losses, the central region contracts.
- The contracting helium core heats up according to the virial theorem.
- T_c increases but does not reach the He ignition temperature.
- The core becomes nearly isothermal : $\epsilon_{He} = 0$, $dT/dr \propto l(m) = 0$.

H-shell burning

- The temperature of the layers above the inert helium core increases and becomes high enough to ignite hydrogen. This layer is called **H-burning shell** (via the CNO cycle)
- In the shell, $\epsilon_H \neq 0 \rightarrow L$, the H-burning shell produces most of the luminosity.

Beyond the main sequence : H shell burning

The envelope expands and cools down

- Due to the **mirror effect** ($\Delta E_{g,env} = -\Delta E_{g,core} > 0$), the envelope expands and cools down.
 - When assuming thermal equilibrium i.e. $\dot{E} = 0$ and $\Delta E_{g,env} = -\Delta E_{g,core}$
 - When there is no thermal equilibrium and $\dot{E} > 0$, $\Delta E_{g,env} = \dot{E} - \Delta E_{g,core}$, leading to an even larger expansion of the envelope.
- As T_{eff} decreases, the H^{-} ions begin to contribute significantly to the opacity. The outer convective region expands inward.
- Rapid phases of evolution from high (blue) to cool (red) temperatures in the HR diagram.

All this process occurs during two successive phases : the subgiant phase and the red giant branch.

The subgiant phase

- The inert core contracts, the central temperature T_c and density ρ_c increase
- The outer convective region expands inward but the envelope still remains dominated by radiative transport (horizontal shift to red in the HR diagram).

The star goes from $T_{eff} = 5728$ K to $T_{eff} = 4819$ K in 2.63 Gyrs

The subgiant phase: structure evolution

From top to bottom : left: evolution of the temperature gradient profile (in relative mass) during the subgiant phase. One can follow the inert He isothermal core growing in mass and the inward expanding of convective envelope. Right : evolution of the hydrogen and helium profiles (in relative mass)

The subgiant phase

Increasing the density of the core causes electron degeneracy to set in

- The mass of the He core increases because the H-shell burning adds helium.
- Degeneracy of electron sets in the He core. The central pressure is dominated by the degenerate electron pressure $P(\rho)$

The mass of the He core keeps increasing because the H-shell burning adds helium.

the Mirror Effect

The physics behind the mirror effect (or why a star becomes a red giant) is still debated. Here a simplified view allows to get some understanding of the process.

- The hydrogen combustion layer above the inert helium core produces all of the star's luminosity,
- it is tightly constrained by the fact that at the temperatures involved, the H combustion is operated by the CNO cycle with the production rate $\epsilon_{nuc} \propto T^{16}$ to T^{20} ,
- This shell must then remain almost in thermal equilibrium.

$$\left(\int_{m_{inf}}^{m_{sup}} \epsilon_{nuc} dm \right) - L \sim 0 \quad (1)$$

- One can write

$$\int_0^M \epsilon_{nuc} dm - L \sim 0$$

where $L = l(m_{sup}) = l(M)$.

- This means the total energy is conserved at all time:

$$\Delta E_{tot} = \left(\left(\int_0^M \epsilon_{nuc} dm \right) - L \right) \Delta t \sim 0$$

the Mirror Effect

- The total variation of energy has two contributions (gravitational and thermal)
 $\Delta E_{tot} = \Delta E_G + \Delta E_{int} \sim 0$.
- Moreover, the virial theorem imposes: $\Delta E_{tot} = \Delta E_G / 2 = -\Delta E_{int}$
- One then has: $\Delta E_G = \Delta E_{G,core} + \Delta E_{G,env} = 0$
- Similarly $\Delta E_{int} = \Delta E_{int,core} + \Delta E_{int,env} = 0$
- As a result: $\Delta E_{G,env} = -\Delta E_{G,core}$ et $\Delta E_{int,env} = -\Delta E_{int,core}$: **Mirror effect.**
- When the helium core no longer has nuclear reactions, it contracts in an attempt to keep its hydrostatic balance under the weight of the shell,

$$R_{core,fin} < R_{core,ini}$$

hence $\Delta E_{G,core} < 0$ which leads to $\Delta E_{int,core} > 0$.

- Since $\Delta E_{G,core} + \Delta E_{G,env} = 0$, alors $\Delta E_{G,env} > 0$ et $\Delta E_{int,env} < 0$, the envelope expands and cools down.
- If the core is in contraction, its internal energy increases under the Virial Theorem and its temperature rises.
- As a result, the expanding envelope cools down. The reverse for an expanding core is also true.

The Red Giant phase

- The convective envelope continues to cool off and to expand inward.
- The envelope becomes so cool that convective transport dominates.
- The star rises the red giant branch (RGB), nearly parallel to the Hayashi line

Ascending the red giant branch (magenta)

The Red Giant phase

- At the same time, the core continues to contract ($R_{core} \downarrow$, $\rho_{core} \uparrow$, $T_{core} \uparrow$).
- More and more helium accumulates around the core, making the mass of the Helium isothermal degenerate core, M_{He} grow.
- The luminosity increases sharply ($L \propto M_{He}^9$, $T_{He} \propto M_{He}^{4/3}$ with M_{He} increases).
- The core gets gradually hotter and denser. The electrons become more and more degenerate^(*).

Evolution in the $\log \rho_c - \log T_c$ diagram: red giant branche (magenta)

(*) electron-degenerate cores (meaning that all low-lying energy states are filled and electron pressure is accordingly dominated by the Pauli exclusion principle)

The Red Giant phase: the first dredge-up

- The convection of the envelope continues to extend inward.

- It eventually reaches regions that have undergone changes in chemical composition as a result of hydrogen combustion.
- The convection-related mixing brings the products of the nuclear reactions to the surface, a process called **first dredge up**.
- Spectroscopic measurements allow to determine surface abundances (N/C and N/O) and test of the physics of the CNO cycle.

Kippenhahn diagram: Evolution of the structure for a star of $1M_{\odot}$ up to the helium flash in a Kippenhahn diagram. Areas in red hatching: nuclear burning areas. Areas in grey: convective regions. (From Maeder and Meynet, 1989)

The Red giant phase: RGB bump

- Fed by hydrogen burning ashes, the inert Helium core grows in mass.
- The H-shell moves upward and pushes the convective envelope back upward.
- The H-shell eventually reaches the discontinuity of chemical composition left behind by the receding convective envelope.
- X decreases in the shell, R , L decreases

The insert shows the location of the bump on the red giant branch. Credit: Christensen-Dalsgaard 2015

The location of the bump on the RGB is not reproduced correctly by standard stellar models: additional mixing below the convective envelope seems necessary

The Red giant phase: RGB bump

From top to bottom : left: evolution of the temperature gradient profile (in relative mass) during the red giant phase. Right : evolution of the hydrogen and helium profiles (in relative mass)

Tip of the Red Giant branch

- At the tip of the RGB, a Sun-like star reaches its maximum size as a red giant.
- The growing He core reaches a mass $M_{\text{He core}} \sim 0.48 M_{\odot}$.
- One can assimilate the core to a white dwarf of mass about $M_c \sim 0.48 M_{\odot}$ and radius $R_c \sim 0.03 R_{\odot}$.
- At the tip of the RGB, a star can lose up to $0.2 M_{\odot}$ before leaving this phase.
- The Sun will remain as a red giant, converting hydrogen to helium in an expanding shell around its core for about 1 billion years.

Evolution in the HR diagram for a mass star $M = 1M_{\odot}$

Onset of core He burning

- At the tip of the RGB, a Sun-like star is massive enough that its core reaches a temperature of $\sim 10^8$ K.
- The He core reaches a mass $M_{\text{He core}} \sim 0.48 M_{\odot}$ which is the minimum mass for igniting He in degenerate conditions
- The core density is very high, so the electrons are degenerate.

Degeneracy

The ignition of He burning occurs in electron degeneracy conditions

Because of the electron degeneracy, the pressure no longer depends on the temperature.

Nonrelativistic degenerate conditions: $P \propto \rho^{5/3}$ $T \propto P/\rho = \rho^{2/3}$

What is the mass of the He core at the onset of He burning?

- At that stage $\rho_{\text{envelope}} / \rho_{\text{core}} \ll 1$
- This results in a decoupling of the core and the envelope then $L(M_{\text{He}})$ and no longer $L(M)$
- Consequence: evolutions for stars with different total mass M but similar core mass M_{He} converge toward the same evolutionary track in a HR diagram
- In degenerate conditions, $T \propto \rho^{2/3}$ and $R \propto M^{-1/3}$ and $\rho \propto M^2$ then : $M^2 \propto T^{3/2}$.
- The onset of He burning at $T \sim 10^8$ K occurs when the He core mass M_{He} reaches a value such that $M_{\text{He}}^2 \propto (10^8 \text{ K})^{3/2}$ which gives $M_{\text{He}} \sim 0.48M_{\odot}$
- For all masses $\leq 1.8M_{\odot}$, the He degenerate core mass at the onset of He burning is $M_{\text{He}} \sim 0.48M_{\odot}$
- (Ignition of helium in NON degenerate condition would have been $M_{\text{He}} \sim 0.33M_{\odot}$)

Why is there a flash ?

- The ignition of He burning generates ϵ_{nuc} which causes a sudden T_c increase while the thermostatic regulation can no longer operate.

Here $P \propto \rho^{5/3}$; $\alpha = 5/3$, $\delta = 0$ and $\delta Q = c_* dT$; $c_* = c_v > 0$

Energy excess $\epsilon \neq 0$, $\delta Q > 0$ then $dT > 0$ heating : thermal run-away

- Ignition of helium combustion in degenerate conditions causes a thermal runaway: the **helium flash**.
- The luminosity experiences a tremendous increase locally.

Why is there a flash ?

- With the new energy supply, the core heats up and expands.
- The dilation of the core leads to a partial lifting of the degeneracy.
- The thermostatic regulation mechanism can then operate again locally leading to expansion of that region, cooling and decrease of the luminosity and contraction of the envelope ($T_{eff} \rightarrow$ slightly)
- After several sub-flashes each closer to the center, the dilation of the core leads to the total lifting of the degeneracy.
- Core He-burning becomes a quiet phase

Luminosity variations (surface, He-burning, H-burning) during helium flash. (Credit O. Pols. 2009)

Toward the Red Clump

- Due to the energy liberation, the dilation of the core leads to a decrease of L .
- Convective transport remains the dominant energy transport. As a consequence, T_{eff} increases little
- The Sun-like star eventually settles on the **red clump** in the HR diagram (GH) for a 110 Myr stable phase.

Helium burning nuclear network

- Helium fusion occurs in the core via the (triple-alpha reaction), providing a new source of energy to the star.
- H-shell burning takes place in a thin shell surrounding the fusing Helium core, but it contributes only a small fraction of the total energy generated.

3 - α reactions:

Carbon -oxygen reaction:

Secondary reactions:

....

The energy production rate $\epsilon_{3\alpha} \propto T^{40}$: the temperature dependence of $\epsilon_{3-\alpha}$ is so high that the core is convective

Abundance profiles

As the star consumes its central Helium, C and O begin to accumulate in the core.

Simultaneous evolution of carbon and oxygen abundance profiles as a function of helium during the helium combustion phase (Credit: O.Pols, 2009)

Evolution of a $1M_{\odot}$ star

Energy release and time scale

- Helium burning releases energy at only about 1/10th the efficiency of the H fusion previous phase.
- For a same luminosity, He burning lifetime is then about 10 times shorter than H burning.
- In addition, L_{He} is higher than $L_{H,MS}$ and the burning lifetime is then even shorter!
($L = \int \epsilon dm$; $\epsilon_{He} \propto T^{30}$ to be compared to $\epsilon_{pp} \propto T^4$).
- A $1M_{\odot}$ red clump star is $\sim 9.5R_{\odot}$, $41L_{\odot}$, $T_{eff} \sim 4724K$; age $\sim 12.234Gyr$.

Credit: wikipedia

III. Evolution of a $1.3M_{\odot}$ star

III. Evolution of $1.3M_{\odot}$ star

Evolution in the HR diagram

For that mass range:

$$L \sim M^{3.5-4.5}; R \sim M^{0.75}; T_{\text{eff}} \propto (R^2/L)^{1/4} \sim M^{0.5-0.7}$$

$\rightarrow L, T_{\text{eff}} \uparrow$ with mass at same X, Z

Nuclear burning process

- $T \sim M/R$, $R \sim M^{0.75}$: T increases with M at same r/R
- T_c increases with the mass M of the stars. High T_c necessary for CNO -cycle (higher Coulomb barrier)

chaîne pp: $T_c \sim 1 - 2 \cdot 10^7 K$; $\rho_c \sim 10^5 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$
cycle CNO: $T_c \sim 2 - 5 \cdot 10^7 K$; $\rho_c \sim 10^4 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$

Consequences:

- Low mass stars with masses $M < 1.1 - 1.2 M_{\odot}$ burn their central hydrogen with the pp chain as the dominant nuclear reaction network.
- Low mass stars with masses $(M > 1.1 - 1.2 M_{\odot})$ burn their central hydrogen with the CNO cycle as the dominant nuclear network.

III. Evolution of $1.3M_{\odot}$ star

Convective core for $M > 1.1 - 1.2M_{\odot}$

Consequences of the temperature dependency of the nuclear energy production:

$$\epsilon_{pp} \sim X^2 \rho T^4 ; \quad \epsilon_{CNO} \sim XX_{CNO} \rho T^{15}$$

- Low mass stars with masses $M < 1.1 - 1.2 M_{\odot}$ have a radiative core in the MS
- Low mass stars with masses ($M > 1.1 - 1.2 M_{\odot}$) have a convective core in the MS

III. Evolution of $1.3M_{\odot}$ star

MS Evolution in the HR diagram

Evolution of the H abundance profile in the lower half of a star with a radiative core (left, $M < \sim 1.1 - 1.2M_{\odot}$) and a convective core (right, $M > 1.1 - 1.2M_{\odot}$)

III. Evolution of $1.3M_{\odot}$ star

The end of the main sequence

- pp chain: $X = 0$ at $r = 0$ then above, the H-shell sets in gradually
- CNO cycle: $X = 0$ in the whole convective core, $\epsilon = 0$, global contraction to compensate, $R \uparrow$ with $L \sim \text{constant}$ then $T_{\text{eff}} \uparrow$

The hook in the evolutionary tracks of the highest mass stars is characteristic of the presence of a convective core in the main sequence.

Open issues in stellar modelling

Main issue : transport processes

Main issues in current stellar modelling deal with transport processes leading in particular to the issue of convective/radiative treatment

- Transport of energy by convection : quite crudely modeled. issue: extension of the convective core
- Transport of angular momentum : issue : solar rotation profile- core rotation of post main sequence stars
- Transport of chemical element : atomic diffusion, radiative acceleration, turbulent mixing
- ...

Extension of convective cores

Stars with masses $M > \sim 1.1M_{\odot}$ have a convective core

What is the problem ?

- Schwarzschild criterion : $\nabla_{rad} > \nabla_{ad}$
- However this indicates the location (radius) where the convective instability ends.
- The fluid elements still have inertia: they overshoot into the overlying radiative region until their velocity vanishes

Extension of convective cores

Stars with masses $M > \sim 1.1M_{\odot}$ have a convective core

Questions:

- How far do the convective elements enter into the radiative region ?
- Is the temperature gradient in the overshooting region initially radiative becoming adiabatic? (In the convective core, convection is very efficient then $\nabla = \nabla_{ad}$)
- Does $\nabla\mu$ in the overshooting region fully vanish and the region becomes uniformly mixed ?

We have some clues about the answers but actually we dont really know.

Extension of convective cores : Why bother ?

- In current modelling : the extension beyond the Schwarzschild limit is modeled in a very pragmatic way :
- Overshoot distance : $d_{ov} = \alpha_{ov} H_p$ or $\alpha_{ov} R_{core}$
- α_{ov} is a free parameter. Some observational constraint indicates $\alpha_{ov} \in (0, 0.15 - 0.2)$

Evolutionary tracks for $1.3M_{\odot}$ models with $\alpha_{ov} = 0$ (cyan) and $\alpha_{ov} = 0.2$ (blue).

For $1.3M_{\odot}$ (α_{ov}) and ($\alpha_{ov} = 0.2$) tracks:
 at $X_c = 10^{-4}$, $age_{\alpha_{ov}=0} = 3.60$ Gyr; $age_{\alpha_{ov}=0.2} = 4.54$ Gyr i.e. 26 % increase!

Extension of convective cores

How to solve the problem?

- Do some physics and approximations (needs constraints from observations for hints and/or validation: seismology)
- Do hydrodynamical simulations (computationally demanding, not easy)
- On the observational side, try to improve/increase the constraints

Transport of angular momentum

The rotation profile $\Omega(r)$ is determined by the angular momentum transport inside the star (and loss at the surface)

- Local conservation of AM: contracting regions accelerate; expanding regions decelerate
- Fully efficient, instantaneous AM transport : solid-body rotation
- The reality may be somewhere in-between depending on the type and efficiency of the AM transport processes

What do the observations tell us ?

Seismic measurements of stellar internal rotation: the Sun

Solar observations solid in the radiative interior, latitudinally differential in the convective region (Talon+ 1997)

Rotation profiles obtained for $1M_{\odot}$ stellar models including rotationally induced transport (Talon+ 1997)

A solution : transport by internal gravity waves generated at the base of the convective envelope

Open issues : transport of angular momentum

Seismic measurements of stellar internal rotation: subgiants and red giants

Seismic measurements of the core rotation as a function of the radius for subgiant ($\sim 2.5R_{\odot}$); red giant ($\sim 2.5R_{\odot} - \sim 8R_{\odot}$) and clump stars ($\sim 10R_{\odot}$); Credit : Deheuvels+2014

Rotation profiles as a function of the local mass for a $1.3M_{\odot}$ early red giant model using various assumptions about the angular momentum transport. None of them allows to reach the low level of the observations ($\sim 1\mu\text{Hz}$). (Credit Marques+2013).

Rotation profiles of stellar models for the Kepler red giant $0.84M_{\odot}$ star KIC 7341231. Imposed solid rotation in the main sequence until the central hydrogen abundance decreases to $X_{\text{C}} = 0.1$ (blue) and $X_{\text{C}} = 0$ (magenta). The impact is significant but not enough to allow to reach the low level of observation (horizontal dashed lines). Credit : Ceillier+2013

Transport of angular momentum : issue

- The impact of internal gravity waves is difficult to implement in 1D stellar evolutionary codes and there are many physical uncertainties
- Comparisons of relevant timescales indicate that gravity waves may be efficient for the subgiants but not for the red giants.
- Other possibilities are under study

Atomic diffusion

Helioseismology has shown that including atomic diffusion is necessary. The impact is significant.

$1M_{\odot}$ stellar evolution. Credit B. Nsamba, PHD 2019

But uncertainties in the diffusion coefficients remain. For stars hotter than the Sun, the convective envelope becomes thin and the surface Helium seems to be too much depleted.

Stellar theoreticians have felt rather comfortable for a long time because their stellar models were reproducing more or less the observations within the error bars.
This is no longer the case with seismic observations!